
Updated catalog of class I late-type stars: Gaia EDR3.

M. Messineo¹, A.G.A. Brown²

¹Key Laboratory for Researches in Galaxies and Cosmology, University of Science and Technology of China, Chinese Academy of Sciences, Hefei, Anhui, 230026, China

²Leiden Observatory, Leiden University, Niels Bohrweg 2, 2333 CA Leiden, The Netherlands

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Abstract

Here we describe on a revised version of the catalog of bright late-type stars by Messineo & Brown (2019) with Gaia EDR3 data.

Key words: stars: evolution — stars: supergiants — stars: massive

1 Introduction

In Messineo & Brown (2019), we presented an infrared photometric catalog of 1,406 stars which are reported as stars with K or M-types and class I in existing works about Galactic red supergiant (RSG) stars, such as the works of Humphreys (1978), Elias et al. (1985), Kleinmann & Hall (1986), Jura & Kleinmann (1990), and Levesque et al. (2005), or listed as stars of class I in the historical spectroscopic catalog of Skiff (2014). By using distances from Gaia DR2 data, and photometric data, we estimated their distances and stellar luminosities. In order to identify highly likely red supergiant stars (RSGs), we grouped the bright stars in areas A, B, C, D, and E, based on their locations in the luminosity versus temperature diagram, with areas A and B being the richest in RSGs. A relationship was identified between the adopted spectral types (temperatures) and average magnitudes.

Here we describe an upgraded version of the catalog of Messineo & Brown (2019) which is based on Gaia EDR3 data, to rederive the average absolute magnitudes per spectral type.

In Sect. 2 we describe the new matches with Gaia EDR3 data points. In Sect. 3 the new average magnitudes are derived.

2 Matches to the K-M I stars in the Gaia EDR3 catalog

In Messineo & Brown (2019), we retrieved 1,342 Gaia DR2 parallaxes for the 1,406 bright late-type stars (K and M types),

candidate RSGs. The number of entries in the published catalog was reduced to 889 because it listed only parallaxes of good quality.

Here, we describe the new Gaia EDR3 matches. We have retrieved 1,354 matches; 1,353 matches were included in the previous DR2 release (1,342 with DR2 parallaxes) and one new match was added for LHO53. The Gaia EDR3 source IDs are identical to those given in DR2 for 1,286 sources; while, in the `gaiaedr3.dr2_neighbourhood` table, for 67 sources, the Gaia DR2 sources are associated with one unique Gaia EDR3 source, but their source IDs are found to be different. As stated in Gaia Collaboration et al. (2021), this occurs frequently (40%) for very bright stars ($G < 5$ mag).

Of the EDR3 matches, 55 Gaia EDR3 matches (4%) presented neighboring sources within $2''$ (generally fainter and at separations larger than $1''$); the Gaia matches assigned to our stars are still the closest to the 2MASS positions and in all but one of the 55 cases their Gaia EDR3 names coincide with their DR2 names.

In Messineo & Brown (2019), distances were estimated as the inverse of the parallaxes, as well as using the geometric posterior probability function by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021). The two distances were compared to set a data filtering. In Messineo & Brown (2019), we restricted our sample to sources with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) > 4$ and $RUWE < 2.7$, where ϖ is the parallax and $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ is the external error of the parallax, and $RUWE$ is the re-normalised unit weight error. The $RUWE$ limit of 2.7 helped us to retain the brightest stars; indeed, the thresh-

Fig. 1. In the upper panels, the inverse distances from DR2 are plotted versus the inverse distances from EDR3. *Upper Left panel:* a constant $\varpi_0 = -0.017$ mas is used. *Upper Right panel:* $\varpi_0(f)$ values are used. In the lower panels, the EDR3 geometric distances by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) are plotted vs. the EDR3 inverse distances. Stars with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})(\text{EDR3}) > 4$ and EDR3 RUWE > 1.4 , $1.4 - 2.7$, and > 2.7 , respectively, are marked with cyan, orange, and red filled circles. *Middle Left panel:* a constant ϖ_0 value of -0.017 mas is used. *Middle Right panel:* $\varpi_0(f)$ values of Lindegren et al. (2021a) are used. *Bottom panel:* The EDR3 inverse distances with individual $\varpi_0(f)$ values (Lindegren et al. 2021a) are plotted versus the inverse distances with a fixed zeropoint (-0.017 mas). Stars with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})(\text{EDR3}) > 4$, 8, and 12 are colored in cyan, orange, and red, respectively.

old value recommended by Lindegren et al. (2018) is 1.4. This data filtering allowed us to keep the DR2 distance deviations (differences between the two estimated distances) within 5%. The $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ is linearly related to the standard internal error; $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) = \sqrt{k^2 \times \sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int})^2 + \sigma_s^2}$. For DR2, when $G < 13$ mag $\sigma_s = 0.021$ mas and when $G > 13$ mag $\sigma_s = 0.043$ mas; while, for EDR3, Lindegren et al. (2021b) measured $\sigma_s = 0.012$ mas and 0.026, respectively. In DR2, the average difference between $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ and $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int})$ for our sample of 889 best stars was 0.0097 mas with a standard deviation $\text{std} = 0.0050$. In EDR3, when using $k = 1.08$ and the new σ_s values of Lindegren et al. (2021b), the average difference is 0.0056 mas ($\text{std} = 0.0032$ mas) for the 1,025 data points with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int}) > 4$. Very recently, a new recipe was developed by Maíz Apellániz et al. (2021), providing a formula for $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ as a function of the G magnitude and RUWE. With the latter recipe, we obtain an average delta between $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ and $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int})$ of 0.014 with $\text{std} = 0.034$ for the 1,025 data points with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int}) > 4$. In conclusion, for the EDR3, we conservatively estimated the $\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ using the recipe by Maíz Apellániz et al. (2021). We retained sources with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) > 4$ (our EDR3 filtering).

In order to estimate the distances, we applied the zero points following the indications of Gaia Collaboration et al. (2021). We used a fixed zero point $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas (derived from quasars), as well as the individual zero points, $\varpi_o(f)$, derived by Lindegren et al. (2021a), which are a function of G magnitudes, colors, and positions. As for DR2, distances from a posterior probability function are available from the work of Bailer-Jones et al. (2021); the distance prior assumes an exponential profile with a direction-dependent scale length as being the stellar density profile. The distances inferred by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) were obtained using the $\varpi - \varpi_o(f)$ values. The mean difference between the inverse distances (with $\varpi_o(f)$ values for consistency) and the geometric distances remain within 5% with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) > 4$ (see Table 1).

861 of the 889 stars filtered in DR2 were reselected by the EDR3 filtering (28 had poorer $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$ from 0.0 to 4.0). 110 Gaia data points with poor quality in the DR2 release have good parallaxes in the EDR3 release. The catalog of good quality parallaxes updated with EDR3 matches contains 972 good stars (out of 1,406). Because six stars had to be removed due to positional misidentifications and new information taken from the literature, as explained in Sect. 4, the good quality stars that remain in the updated catalog number 966.

The 889 $\varpi(\text{DR2})$ values with good quality correlate well with their corresponding $\varpi(\text{EDR3})$ values with a median value of 0.048 mas, a mean value of 0.111 mas with $\text{std} = 0.278$ mas. The mean $\varpi(\text{DR2}) + 0.029 - \varpi(\text{EDR3}) - 0.017 = 0.129$ mas with $\text{std} = 0.318$ mas. The mean $\varpi(\text{DR2}) + 0.029 - \varpi(\text{EDR3}) + \varpi_o(f) = 0.108$ mas with $\text{std} = 0.276$ mas. The mean ϖ of our sample decreases in the EDR3 release (from 5% to 30%) and

distances are larger, as shown in Table 2. The choice of the fixed zero point or $\varpi_o(f)$ appears of secondary importance (causing variations from 0 to 9 %), but is influential beyond 4.5 kpc (>10%). The adopted filtering $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})(\text{EDR3}) > 4$ is based on the comparison of the geometric distances by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) and inverse distances (to be within 5%). After having set this limit, we re-analyze the effect of the zero points as a function of distances. In Fig. 1, we show the relationship between the inverse distances obtained with a fixed ϖ_o or with the $\varpi_o(f)$ values and the geometric distances by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021). Beyond 4.5 kpc, the $\varpi_o(f)$ values yield distances significantly shorter than those with a fixed ϖ_o , as described in Table 3. There is an acceptable level of agreement (within 200 pc) between the various distances when considering the filtered data points ($\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})(\text{EDR3}) > 4$) within 4.5 kpc, as tabulated in Table 3. This effect of the zeropoints is negligible for $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})(\text{EDR3}) > 12$, which extend to 4 kpc. We conclude that Gaia EDR3 parallaxes of individual stars can safely be analyzed up to distances of about 4.5 kpc. It is likely that improved calibrations will render the impact of the zero point corrections much smaller in the next release.

Poggio et al. (2021) use the $\varpi_o(f)$ corrections of Lindegren et al. (2021a) for Cepheids and estimate a period-luminosity relationship in agreement with that previously obtained with Gaia DR2 data. Poggio et al. (2021) uses the fixed ϖ_o for their sample of globular clusters. However, their data points are within 4 kpc. For globular clusters from 4 to 8 kpc, Maíz Apellániz et al. (2021) found distances in agreement with those in the literature by using the $\varpi_o(f)$ corrections by Lindegren et al. (2021a).

As Lindegren (2020) warns, the calibration of bright late-type stars may be more complex, due to their large radii and brightness fluctuations (Chiavassa et al. 2011; Pasquato et al. 2011). The RUWE values must be carefully analyzed as this may provide indications for unresolved binaries and particular structures in the stellar atmospheres or envelopes (Humphreys et al. 2021). By using the radio parallaxes of AGBs and RSGs listed by Xu et al. (2019) and Gaia EDR3 data, we obtained only seven matches with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{int})(\text{EDR3}) > 4$, $\text{RUWE} < 1.4$, including 2 RSGs (see Table 4); the seven distances range from a few pc to about 3 kpc. The mean fractional differences are $(\varpi(\text{EDR3}) - \varpi_o(f) - \varpi(\text{radio}))/\varpi(\text{radio}) = -0.06$ with $\text{std} = 0.16$, and $(\varpi(\text{EDR3}) + 0.017 - \varpi(\text{radio}))/\varpi(\text{radio}) = -0.09$ with $\text{std} = 0.14$. The mean differences are $(1./(\varpi(\text{EDR3}) - \varpi_o(f)) - 1./\varpi(\text{radio})) \times 1000 = -7.123$ pc with $\text{std} = 147.66$ pc, and $(1./(\varpi(\text{EDR3}) + 0.017) - 1./\varpi(\text{radio})) \times 1000 = 49.44$ pc with $\text{std} = 112.938$ pc.

2.1 The RUWE parameter

In the EDR3 release, the number of stars in our sample with large RUWE values is four times larger than in the DR2 release,

Table 1. Average differences, Δ , between the inverse distances and the geometric distances by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) as a function of ϖ/σ_ϖ .

Δ -type	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)	Nstar	$\langle \Delta \rangle$ (dist) [pc]	std [pc]	$\langle \Delta \rangle$ (DM) [mag]	std [mag]
$r_{\text{BJ(DR2)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{DR2}} + 0.029)$	2		-6	124	0.02	0.09
$r_{\text{BJ(DR2)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{DR2}} + 0.029)$	3		3	44	0.01	0.05
$r_{\text{BJ(DR2)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{DR2}} + 0.029)$	4	889	4	22	0.01	0.03
$r_{\text{BJ(DR2)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{DR2}} + 0.029)$	5		5	13	0.01	0.02
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017)(1)$	2	1070	-84	275	0.04	0.13
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017)(1)$	3	1009	-84	187	0.03	0.06
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017)(1)$	4	966	-80	153	0.02	0.04
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017)(1)$	5	925	-75	130	0.02	0.03
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	2	1070	48	167	0.04	0.13
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	3	1009	29	69	0.03	0.06
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	4	966	24	49	0.02	0.04
$r_{\text{BJ(EDR3)}} - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	5	925	22	40	0.02	0.03
$1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017) - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))$	2	1070	132	227	0.09	0.10
$1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017) - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))$	3	1009	114	180	0.08	0.09
$1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017) - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))$	4	966	105	158	0.08	0.08
$1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} + 0.017) - 1/(\varpi_{\text{EDR3}} - \varpi_o(f))$	5	925	97	138	0.08	0.08

$\langle \Delta \rangle$ (DM) is the average difference of the Distance Moduli inferred from the two used distances. $\langle \Delta \rangle$ (dist) is the average difference of the two used distances. The tabulation is given for Gaia DR2 data points and Gaia EDR3 data points, for ϖ/σ_ϖ (est) from 2 to 5. In the EDR3(1) rows, the inverse distances for the Gaia EDR3 release are estimated with a fixed $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2021), while in the EDR3(2) rows with the $\varpi_o(f)$ values by Lindegren et al. (2021a).

Table 2. The mean ratios between the $\varpi(\text{DR2}) + 0.029$ values and the $\varpi(\text{EDR3})$ values (two types of zero point corrections) as a function of distance.

Nstar	$\varpi(\text{DR2}(1))/$ $\varpi(\text{EDR3}(2))$	std	$\varpi(\text{DR2}(1))/$ $\varpi(\text{EDR3}(1))$	std	conditions
888	1.23	0.77	1.28	0.79	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7
6	1.48	0.29	1.61	0.30	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; >4 kpc
75	1.33	0.44	1.42	0.50	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; 3-4 kpc
279	1.19	0.32	1.25	0.35	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; 2-3 kpc
253	1.13	0.26	1.13	0.28	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; 1-2 kpc
135	1.02	0.11	1.03	0.11	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; 0.5-1 kpc
78	1.05	0.15	1.05	0.15	ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(DR2) > 4 ; RUWE(DR2) < 2.7; ϖ/σ_ϖ (est)(EDR3) > 4; <0.5 kpc

In the $\varpi(\text{DR2}(1))$, the parallaxes are corrected with a fixed $\varpi_o = -0.029$ mas. In the $\varpi(\text{EDR3}(1))$, the parallaxes are corrected with a fixed $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2021), while in the $\varpi(\text{EDR3}(2))$ with the $\varpi_o(f)$ values by Lindegren et al. (2021a).

Table 3. Average differences, Δ , between the calculated distances of data points with $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(est)(EDR3) > 4$ per bin of distance.

Δ -type	Nstar	$\langle \Delta \rangle$ (dist) [pc]	std [pc]	median [pc]	bin of dist(EDR3(2))
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	219	-20	93	-8	dist < 1 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	263	-165	311	-84	1kpc \geq dist < 2 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	291	-439	572	-408	2kpc \geq dist < 3 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	97	-1164	974	-1129	3kpc \geq dist < 4.5 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	13	-5492	6482	-3215	dist \geq 4.5 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	219	-15	92	-7	dist < 1 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	263	-122	294	-62	1kpc \geq dist < 2 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	291	-315	538	-292	2kpc \geq dist < 3 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	97	-887	852	-847	3kpc \geq dist < 4.5 kpc
$1/(\varpi_{DR2} + 0.029) - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	13	-4987	6852	-2499	dist \geq 4.5 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	223	-2	9	-2	dist < 1 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	268	-27	40	-23	1kpc \geq dist < 2 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	312	-86	96	-97	2kpc \geq dist < 3 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	134	-200	182	-212	3kpc \geq dist < 4.5 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} + 0.017)(1)$	29	-572	373	-626	dist \geq 4.5 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	223	2	8	0	dist < 1 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	268	15	25	7	1kpc \geq dist < 2 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	312	36	50	24	2kpc \geq dist < 3 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	134	49	71	34	3kpc \geq dist < 4.5 kpc
$r_{BJ(EDR3)} - 1/(\varpi_{EDR3} - \varpi_o(f))(2)$	29	36	121	21	dist \geq 4.5 kpc

In the EDR3(1) raws, the inverse distances for the Gaia EDR3 release are estimated with a fixed $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2021), while in the EDR3(2) raws with the $\varpi_o(f)$ values by Lindegren et al. (2021a).

Table 4. Radio ϖ values of known RSGs with also Gaia EDR3 ϖ values of good quality (RUWE-EDR3 < 1.4, $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(int) > 4$).

Name	Radio ϖ	EDR3 ϖ	EDR3(1)	EDR3(2)	RUWE-EDR3	$\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(int)$
PZ Cas	0.356 ± 0.026	0.355 ± 0.041	0.372	0.394	1.093	8.668
IRC60370	0.4 ± 0.025	0.363 ± 0.029	0.380	0.405	1.057	12.524

In the EDR3(1) raws, the ϖ values for the Gaia EDR3 release are corrected with a fixed $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas (Gaia Collaboration et al. 2021), while in the EDR3(2) raws with the $\varpi_o(f)$ values by Lindegren et al. (2021a).

and the maximum RUWE value (10-14) is much higher than that measured in DR2 (2.7). We analyzed the RUWE values as a function of ϖ/σ_{ϖ} and G -mag, as shown in Fig. 2. In EDR3, a large number of data points appears to have a RUWE value above 1.4 (the threshold value recommended in Lindegren et al. 2018); from the 23 sources of DR2 to the 79 sources of EDR3 (out of 966 good EDR3). The average RUWE of the sample is consistent with that of the previous release; in DR2, the median RUWE was 0.99, the mean RUWE was 1.21 with std=1.09. In EDR3, the mean RUWE is 1.09 with std=0.52, and the median value is 0.98. The data points above RUWE 1.4 in DR2 also remain as such in EDR3.

55 stars out of the 966 stars with good Gaia EDR3 parallaxes are reported as spectroscopic RSGs in binary systems by Pantaleoni González et al. (2020), Neugent et al. (2019), Skiff (2014), and Burki & Mayor (1983) (see Table 5). 40 of them are located among the 474 stars of areas A and B of the luminosity versus temperature diagram described in Messineo & Brown

(2019); these are the most probable areas populated by RSGs. The known binaries represent 8.4% of the sample stars in areas A and B. 68 of the 966 stars are reported as candidate binaries by Kervella et al. (2019) and Brandt (2021) based on the analysis of Hipparcos and Gaia DR2 and EDR3 proper motions (signal to noise of the anomaly detected in the proper motions > 3), of which 32 are located in areas A and B. 17 of those coincide with known binaries.

Most of the binaries collected from the lists of Pantaleoni González et al. (2020), Skiff (2014), Neugent et al. (2019), and Burki & Mayor (1983) are binaries optically detected or stars that presented an excess in the UV bands (e.g. Parsons & Ake 1998), and, therefore, spectroscopically observed for confirming the binary system. In Fig. 2, it appears that a large value of the RUWE parameter is often a signature of a binary system. If we count those stars closer than 2 kpc and with RUWE > 1.4, 13.4% of them are found to be known binaries, and 24.6% by also counting as candidate binaries those with

Fig. 2. *Upper Left panel:* The EDR3 RUWE values vs. the G magnitudes for all the source in our sample (blue dots). The large brown dots indicate sources for which $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) > 4$, while the dark-green crosses indicate sources without color information. Known binaries (see text) are marked with red crosses. Gaia data points with neighbors within $2''$ are encircled. The horizontal lines indicate the curves $RUWE = 1.4$ (in red), $RUWE = 2.7$ (in gray), and $RUWE = 6.3$ (in green). *Upper Right panel:* The EDR3 RUWE values versus the inverse distances of bright stars located in areas A and B of the M_{bol} versus T_{eff} diagram of Messineo & Brown (2019), i.e. highly likely RSGs. Large brown dots mark data points with good ϖ , $\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est}) > 4$. Red crosses mark known binaries. Filled cyan circles indicate the coincidences with the candidate binaries of Kervella et al. (2019) and Brandt (2021). Gaia data points with neighbors within $2''$ are encircled. *Lower Right panel:* The EDR3 RUWE values are plotted vs. the T_{eff} values. Bright cold stars from areas A & B are marked with black circles, and those known to be in binary systems with cyan crosses. If the RUWE values are larger than 1.4 the circles (stars in areas A and B) and crosses (binary) are colored red. The location of VV Cep (M2lab+B0-2V) is marked with a green filled circle. *Upper Left panel:* The luminosities are plotted vs. the T_{eff} values. Symbols are as in the Lower Right panel. Most of the largest EDR3 RUWE values belong to stars in area B (and not A), i.e. are fainter than the AGB limit ($M_{\text{bol}} = -7.1$ mag). Tracks of stars from 7 to 20 M_{\odot} from Ekström et al. (2012) are over-plotted. The two magenta-dashed lines mark the location of the AGB limit and tip of the red giant branch.

Table 5. List of K-M stars included in the catalog which are reported in the literature as a binary system, but are not included in the list of binaries of Pantaleoni González et al. (2020).

Name	Gaia EDR3 name	fHG*	Sp.type	Reference	CMD-Area ⁺	$\varpi/\sigma_{\varpi}(\text{est})$	RUWE3
HD 105563 A	6054081691687449728	1	M1 +B	1	A	13.7	1.1
HD 42543	3425055656275589632	0	M1 Ia-ab +?	2	A	4.1	1.3
HD 143183	5932748487665645824	0	M3 Ia +B/F	1	A	4.8	0.9
HD 72838	5323140101109547904	1	K1 I-II +A/F	1	B	26.3	1.2
HD 200945	2165179226821714176	0	K2 Ib +?	2	B	22.2	1.1
HD 200905	2162316545207257600	1	K5 Ib +?	2	B	11.6	2.3
HD 37387	3404384322275638016	0	K1 Ib +?	2	B	21.6	1.0
HD 45829	3324706116226617856	1	K0 Iab +?	2	B	25.2	1.1
HD 145384	5932963991897373184	0	M0 +F/G	1	B	13.5	0.9
HD 106505	6054426113711871616	0	M0 +B	1	B	23.0	1.0
HD 4817	427499264872921472	1	K2.5 +B5-6V	1,3	B	22.6	0.9
HR 1112	474128453493428224	1	K4 Ib +?	2	D	24.7	1.1
HD 130205/6	5878286859176627840	1	K5 +B/A	1	D	40.3	0.9
CD-60 5086	5866604754296590720	0	M0 +B8III	1	E	4.8	3.8
HD 151184	5929865396347532928	0	M2 I +A/F	1	E	19.5	1.7
CD-38 12283	4036852822616282240	0	M3 +FI	1	F	7.5	0.7
HD 31895	201787497832204288	1	K3 Ib +?	2	F	47.4	1.0
LS IV +07 6	4286114238836965760	0	K5 +FI	1	F	9.1	3.9
BD+09 4226	4301856530946650112	0	K0 Ib +?	2	F	29.6	1.8

References: 1= Skiff (2014); 2=Burki & Mayor (1983); 3=Neugent et al. (2019).

* fHG=1 if the star is reported in the catalog of Kervella et al. (2019) with anomalous motions (21 stars have an anomaly detection $\sigma > 3$) or in the catalog of Brandt (2021) with a $\sigma > 3$ and a $\chi > 12$ (60 stars).

8 of the 21 stars found with anomalous motion in DR2 but not in the EDR3 catalog are also retained (because of likely fluctuations in the σ cut).

⁺ Area occupied in the M_{bol} values versus temperatures diagram as defined in Messineo & Brown (2019).

accelerated proper motions. If we consider only the 10 (12) known (candidate) binaries out of 57 stars closer than 2 kpc, with RUWE > 1.4, located in areas A and B, we increase the fraction to 17.5 (21.0)%, respectively. Eventually, when considering the 10 (12) binaries out of the 22 closer than 2 kpc, with RUWE > 1.4, located in areas A and B, and detected with the Hipparcos satellite, we increase the fraction to 45.5 (54.5)%, respectively; in the latter case, but with RUWE < 1.4, the fraction decreases to 16.9 (25.4)%.

Analogous results are reported in the work on eclipsing binaries by Stassun & Torres (2021); the RUWE parameter is a marker of an unresolved binary system, as in these systems the photocenter does not coincide with the barycenter and the goodness-of-fit of the Gaia EDR3 astrometric solution is degraded. For U-Monocerotis (RV Tau variable system, which hosts a KOIbpv post-AGB), Vega et al. (2021) report a high RUWE value (EDR3 RUWE=5.4).

3 Average bolometric magnitudes of RSGs per spectral type

Bolometric magnitudes were estimated as in Messineo & Brown (2019). For each star, one estimate of M_{bol} was obtained with the bolometric corrections, BC_{K_S} , of Levesque et al. (2005), as well as with the integration of flux measurements covering from I-band to 24 μm , and with extrapolations at the two extremities. We used the same routine as in Messineo & Brown (2019), with a slightly improved normalisation of the blackbody extrapolation at the shorter wavelength side. The two sets of magnitudes differ in average of 0.13 mag with std=0.07 mag.

Messineo & Brown (2019) provides the average bolometric magnitudes, M_{bol} , per spectral type of reference RSGs, based on the DR2 ϖ values. As in Messineo & Brown (2019), here we estimate the average magnitudes with the M_{bol} vector calculated with the BC_{K_S} and with the DM from Bailer-Jones et al. (2021). The new average M_{bol} values made with Gaia EDR3 distances appear 0.22 mag brighter than those published in Messineo & Brown (2019), as it appears in Fig. 3. This is due to the decrease of the ϖ values that occurred from DR2 to EDR3 (see Table 2).

The new average magnitudes per spectral type are presented in Table 6.¹

4 Notes on individual stars

The catalog has the same identification numbers as given in Messineo & Brown (2019) for the common stars. The list of stars in Messineo & Brown (2019) is based on existing Galactic compilations of RSGs, for example by Humphreys (1978), Elias et al. (1985), Kleinmann & Hall (1986), Jura & Kleinmann (1990), Caron et al. (2003), Levesque et al. (2005), Figer et al. (2006), Davies et al. (2008), and Verhoelst et al. (2009), Blum et al. (2003), Comerón et al. (2004), Clark et al. (2009), Liermann et al. (2009), Rayner et al. (2009), Negueruela et al. (2010), Negueruela et al. (2011), Verheyen et al. (2012), Dorda et al. (2016), Messineo et al. (2017), Dorda et al. (2018), and on the spectroscopic catalog of Skiff (2014) (catalog retrieved from CDS on Nov 2016). It yielded a collection of 1,406 stars, of which 889 passed the Gaia DR2 data filtering in Messineo & Brown (2019) and 996 with EDR3 data.

As annotated in the README file to the tables of Messineo & Brown (2019), the catalog contains three extra entries by mistake due to typos in the alias name reported in the literature.

ID=386, CD-57 3502 (EDR3 ID=5350921534458832128) is a wrong alias in Elias et al. 1985. This entry can be ignored. The correct name is CPD -57 3502, which is also inserted.

ID=443, CPD-59 4549 (EDR3 ID=6056404581808869504) is a wrong alias in Humphreys et al 1978. This entry can be ignored. The correct star CD-59 4459 is also listed in the catalog.

ID=565, HD 142686 (EDR3 ID=6246928609463623168) is a wrong alias in Humphreys et al 1978. This entry can be ignored. The correct star is HD 142696, which is also inserted in the catalog.

There are a few recent updates on individual stars. The spectral type of GSC 3997-1983 (Gaia EDR3=2013402229386855296) was changed from M1 to K6 (Dutta et al. 2018).

The spectral type of ID=588 (CPD-53 7416, EDR3 ID=5932571947396952192) was changed from K2 Ib-II to G8 II (Alonso-Santiago et al. 2017).

The source ID=702 (UCAC2 34720429, EDR3 ID=4301238983369942272) is misidentified with the K2I IRAS 19356+0754 star in Suárez et al. (2006).

We used the online version of the Skiff catalog available at CDS (as this is already cross-referenced with the CDS archive). Since, 2016 the Skiff (2014) catalog at CDS has been updated. With the 2018 release in CDS, we counted 96 additional stars of class I, of which only 13 had luminosities above the tip of the red giant branch tip. With the current version of 2020 in CDS, the candidate RSGs in addition to those listed in Messineo & Brown (2019) amount to 123. These stars are currently under analysis (photometry and literature) and we will include them with the next Gaia release.

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¹ The M_{bol} of the individual stars with good EDR3 ϖ values are available in this github.com/mariamessineo/KMclassI. 474 out of the 966 stars analyzed are located in the areas A and B of the luminosity versus temperature diagram, as defined in (Messineo & Brown 2019).

Table 6. Magnitudes per spectral type of reference RSGs. Geometric distances from Bailer-Jones et al. (2021) are here used.

Nstar	Sp.Type	M_{bol} [mag]	$M_{bol(int)}$ [mag]	M_K [mag]	M_V [mag]	$M_{bol}(fix)$ [mag]	$M_K(fix)$ [mag]	$M_V(fix)$ [mag]
1	K0.5–K0	-4.72	-4.92	-7.12	-4.80	-4.73	-7.13	-4.81
2	K1.5–K1	-4.38± 0.70	-4.59± 0.70	-6.84± 0.71	-4.61± 0.59	-4.39± 0.70	-6.86± 0.71	-4.63± 0.59
7	K2.5–K2	-4.93± 0.37	-5.16± 0.36	-7.44± 0.37	-5.07± 0.38	-4.93± 0.36	-7.44± 0.36	-5.07± 0.38
12	K3.5–K3	-5.08± 0.35	-5.38± 0.35	-7.63± 0.35	-4.92± 0.25	-5.09± 0.35	-7.64± 0.35	-4.93± 0.26
3	K4.5–K4	-4.99± 0.42	-5.17± 0.42	-7.59± 0.42	-4.87± 0.51	-5.00± 0.41	-7.59± 0.41	-4.87± 0.50
6	K5.5–K5	-5.56± 0.33	-5.64± 0.34	-8.20± 0.33	-4.81± 0.35	-5.60± 0.34	-8.24± 0.34	-4.85± 0.35
8	M0.5–M0	-6.37± 0.23	-6.49± 0.24	-9.06± 0.23	-5.01± 0.20	-6.37± 0.23	-9.07± 0.22	-5.02± 0.19
16	M1.5–M1	-6.57± 0.15	-6.69± 0.16	-9.31± 0.15	-5.20± 0.11	-6.61± 0.15	-9.35± 0.15	-5.24± 0.12
39	M2.5–M2	-6.87± 0.12	-7.00± 0.12	-9.67± 0.12	-5.02± 0.14	-6.92± 0.12	-9.73± 0.12	-5.07± 0.14
23	M3.5–M3	-7.64± 0.18	-7.77± 0.18	-10.49± 0.18	-4.73± 0.18	-7.67± 0.17	-10.52± 0.17	-4.76± 0.18
7	M4.5–M4	-6.83± 0.55	-6.96± 0.56	-9.72± 0.55	-3.62± 0.62	-6.87± 0.54	-9.76± 0.54	-3.66± 0.62
2	M5.5–M5	-7.79± 0.13	-7.94± 0.11	-10.75± 0.13	-4.22± 0.33	-7.78± 0.12	-10.74± 0.12	-4.22± 0.32

The M_{bol} , $M_{bol(int)}$, M_K , and M_V quantities are estimated with the geometric distances by Bailer-Jones et al. (2021).

The M_{bol} values are with the BC_{K_S} of Levesque et al. (2005).

The $M_{bol(int)}$ values are obtained integrating under the stellar energy distribution.

The $M_{bol}(fix)$, $M_K(fix)$, $M_V(fix)$ are estimated with the EDR3 inverse distances and $\varpi_o = -0.017$ mas.

Fig. 3. This is an updated version of the figure number 7 appearing in Messineo & Brown (2019). The average M_{bol} values per spectral type are plotted versus the T_{eff} values. The average M_{bol} estimated from the BC_{K_S} is used to maximise the number of points. Black filled circles indicate the M_{bol} values with EDR3 data for the sample of reference RSGs (the M_{bol} with DR2 values are shown in red). Cyan crosses show the average M_{bol} values obtained with EDR3 data for class Ia and IaB stars (for comparison, the previously M_{bol} with DR2 values are shown in light orange).

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